

POLAND

POLAND

INNOVATION IN EDUCATION**Ro'zixon Yakubjanova¹****Qambarova Gulshona Baxodirjon qizi²**¹⁻²Andijon davlat chet tillari instituti

guli280999@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7543196>**Abstract**

This article presents the advantages of using innovative pedagogy in improving the quality of education.

Key words: method,innovation,latin,education,pedagogy,technology

Today, the development of education has become a priority for every country. All scientists are trying to find different ways to move forward in this area. In particular, the use of modern methods, innovation, is considered the best way. .

First of all, what is innovation? The word "innovation" is derived from the Latin word "inovatis" (in-into, novus-new, innovation), which translates as "introduction of innovation, positive change, renewal ". Innovations are scientifically and practically based, focused on a specific goal in any field and highly effective. In the years of independence, raising the quality and efficiency of education to the level of modern requirements has become one of the priorities of state policy. The priorities of education, the content and structure of education are changing, new standards are being introduced, the quality of education is rising to a new, higher level of development. requires taking it to a new level. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev emphasized, we must consider it our primary task to improve the activities of all levels of the education system in accordance with modern requirements. loving, relying on their own knowledge and talent, and independently acquiring knowledge through the use of modern information and communication technologies, contributing to the becoming a strong state of Uzbekistan, comprehensively harmonious, healthy upbringing . These tasks are carried out, first of all, through effective lessons. This requires our educators to be able to use pedagogical innovations. As for the history of pedagogical innovation, the term "innovative pedagogy" and its specific research appeared in Western Europe and the United States in the 60s of the twentieth century. Researched in the works of Kan-Kalik, NVKuzmina, V.A.Slatenin, AISherbakov. These studies are presented in terms of innovative practice and dissemination of best pedagogical practices. H. Barnet, J. Bassett, D. Hamilton, N. Gross, M. Mayez, A. Haylock, D. Chen, R. Edem. Now that we have an idea of how to apply it in the

classroom, we can see the innovation in the form of a lesson in the following way. a) Standard lesson - the structure of the lesson does not change. b) Non-standard lesson - the structure of the lesson changes. c) Virtual lesson - distance learning. The concept of "new" is central to pedagogical innovation. There is also an interest in private, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogy. Private innovation V.A. Slastenin found that in the current modernization involves the renewal of one of the elements of a particular system product. Conditional innovation is the combination of known elements that lead to complex and progressive innovation. Innovation is a tool: a new method, technique, technology, and so on. Vizagvyazinsky described the new concept in pedagogy as not only an idea, but also untapped approaches, methods, technologies, but the elements of this pedagogical process are complex or separate elements, which are the beginnings of effective solutions to educational problems in changing conditions and situations.

In short, the innovation process consists of a system of structures and laws. and on the basis of the achievements of psychological sciences.

References:

1. Qambarova G. B. Q. Et Al. Analysis Of Scientific Works On "Phonetics" In The World During 2000-2022 //Science And Education. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 12. – C. 1073-1079.
2. Usmonov M. T. Virtual Protected Networks. International Journal Of Academic Pedagogical Research (Ijapr) Issn: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 55-57.
3. Usmonov M. T. What Is Solving The Problem? Methods Of Solving Text Problems. International Journal Of Engineering And Information Systems (Ijeais) Issn: 2643-640x Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 56-58.
4. Usmonov M. T. Fundamentals Of Symmetric Cryptosystem. International Journal Of Academic And Applied Research (Ijaar) Issn: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 36-40.
5. Usmonov M. T. General Concepts Of Mathematics. International Journal Of Academic Information Systems Research (Ijaisr) Issn: 2643-9026 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 14-16.
6. Usmonov M. T. Identification And Authentication. International Journal Of Academic Pedagogical Research (Ijapr) Issn: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 39-47.
7. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection And Its Types. International Journal Of Academic And Applied Research (Ijaar) Issn: 2643-9603 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 1-4.

8. Usmonov M. T. Information Protection In Wireless Communication Systems. International Journal Of Academic Pedagogical Research (Ijapr) Issn: 2643-9123 Vol. 5 Issue 1, January - 2021, Pages: 61-64.
9. М Усмонов - Academic Research In Modern Science, 2022. Как Построить Линию В Полярной Системе Координат. Pages: 93-105.
10. Um Tulqin O'g'li - Ta'lim Va Rivojlanish Tahlili Onlayn Ilmiy ..., 2022. Determinantlar Nazariyasi. Pages: 232-248.
11. R Jo'rayev, M Usmonov - Solution Of Social Problems In Management And ..., 2022. Oziq-Ovqat Sanoatining Dolzarbligi Va Samaradorligi. Pages: 19-25
12. М Усмонов - Academic Research In Modern Science, 2022. Как Построить Линию В Полярной Системе Координат. Pages: 93-105
13. М Усмонов - Development And Innovations In Science, 2022. Векторное Произведение Векторов. Смешанное Произведение Векторов. Pages: 33-52.
14. М Усмонов - Models And Methods In Modern Science, 2022. Дискретный Вариационный Ряд. Полигон Частот И Эмпирическая Функция Распределения. Pages: 27-35.
15. М Усмонов - Инновационные Исследования В Науке, 2022. Интервальный Вариационный Ряд. Гистограмма Относительных Частот. Pages: 43-52
16. М Усмонов - Международная Конференция Академических Наук, 2022. Формулы Деления Отрезка В Данном Отношении. Формулы Координат Середины Отрезка. Pages: 17-26.
17. Um Tulqin O'g'li, Qf Ergash O'g'li - Ta'lim Va Rivojlanish Tahlili Onlayn Ilmiy ..., 2022. Yer Osti Suvlarining Fizik Xossalari, Kimyoviy Tarkibi, Harakati Va Gruntlarning Suv O'tkazuvchanligi, Filtratsiya Qonuni. Pages: 219-222.
18. Um Tulqin O'g'li, Qf Ergash O'g'li - Ta'lim Va Rivojlanish Tahlili Onlayn Ilmiy ..., 2022. Vektor Va Skalyar Maydonlar. Gradiyent Va Yo'nalish Bo'yicha Hosila. Divergensiya Va Rotor. Sath Chiziqlari. Gradiyent Maydonlar. Oqimlar. Pages: 172-187.
19. Um Tulqin O'g'li, Qf Ergash O'g'li - Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy ..., 2022. Fure Qatori Va Uning Tadbiqlari. Pages: 21-33.
20. O'G'li, U. M. T. ., & O'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). Fure Qatori Va Uning Tadbiqlari. Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal, 21-33. Retrieved From [Http://Sciencebox.Uz/Index.Php/Jis/Article/View/1152](http://Sciencebox.Uz/Index.Php/Jis/Article/View/1152)
21. O'G'li, U. M. T. ., & O'g'li, Q. F. E. . (2022). Darajali Qatorlar. Darajali Qatorlarning Yaqinlashish Radiusi Va Sohasi. Teylor Formulasi Va Qatori.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

Ijtimoiy Fanlarda Innovasiya Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnali, 8–20. Retrieved From
[Http://Www.Sciencebox.Uz/Index.Php/Jis/Article/View/1151](http://Www.Sciencebox.Uz/Index.Php/Jis/Article/View/1151)

22. Мтў Усмонов, Хум Ўғли - Central Asian Research Journal For
Interdisciplinary ..., 2022. Равномерное Распределение Вероятностей. 15-24